

COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS OF HEAT EXCHANGER USING WATER BASED NANO FLUIDS

D.V. Raghunatha Reddy

Assistant Professor, Dept. of Mechanical Engineering,
Sridevi women's engineering college Hyderabad, India – 500075.

Abstract:—A heat exchanger is a piece of equipment built for efficient heat transfer from one medium to another. The media may be separated by a solid wall, so that they never mix, or they may be in direct contact. They are widely used in refrigeration, air conditioning, power plants, chemical plants, petrochemical plants, petroleum, natural gas processing, and sewage treatment. The classic example of a heat exchanger is found in internal combustion engines in which a circulating fluid known as engine coolant flows through radiator coils and air flows past the coils, which cools the coolant and heats the incoming air.

An experiment is done with different fluid and materials like water and carbon mixed with water, the heat transfer for the respective materials are calculated. Analysis is again carried out in Ansys Fluent, by first creating the given heat Exchanger with the help of GAMBIT (pre processor for Ansys Fluent) and the results are compared respectively with experimental results.

Key words: Nanofluids, LMTD, ANSYS, CFD, heat exchanger, Meshing

1. INTRODUCTION

A heat exchanger is a device that is used to transfer thermal energy (enthalpy) between two or more fluids, between a solid surface and a fluid, or between solid particulates and a fluid, at different temperatures and in thermal contact. In heat exchangers, there are usually no external heat and work interactions. Typical applications involve heating or cooling of a fluid stream of concern and evaporation or condensation of single- or multi-component fluid streams. In other applications, the objective may be to recover or reject heat, or sterilize, pasteurize, fractionate, distill, concentrate, crystallize, or control a process fluid. In a few heat exchangers, the fluids exchanging heat are in direct contact. In most heat exchangers, heat transfer between fluids takes place through a separating wall or into and out of a wall in a transient manner. In many heat exchangers, the fluids are separated by a heat transfer surface, and ideally they do not mix or leak. Such exchangers are referred to as direct transfer type, or simply recuperator. In contrast,

exchangers in which there is intermittent heat exchange between the hot and cold fluids—via thermal energy storage and release through the exchanger surface or matrix—are referred to as indirect transfer type, or simply regenerators. Such exchangers usually have fluid leakage from one fluid stream to the other, due to pressure differences and matrix rotation/valve switching. Common examples of heat exchangers are shell-and tube exchangers, automobile radiators, condensers, evaporators, air pre heaters, and cooling towers. If no phase change occurs in any of the fluids in the exchanger, it is sometimes referred to as a sensible heat exchanger. There could be internal thermal energy sources in the exchangers, such as in electric heaters and nuclear fuel elements. Combustion and chemical reaction may take place within the exchanger, such as in boilers, fired heaters, and fluidized-bed exchangers. Mechanical devices may be used in some exchangers such as in scraped surface exchangers, agitated vessels, and stirred tank reactors. Heat transfer in the separating wall of a recuperator generally takes place by conduction. Evaporation, and conduction of the working fluid inside the heat pipe. In general, if the fluids are immiscible, the separating wall may be eliminated, and the interface between the fluids replaces a heat transfer surface, as in a direct-contact heat exchanger.

2. OBJECTIVES OF PRESENT WORK

As is evident from the diversity of application areas, the study of flow and heat transfer in exchanger is very important for the technology of today and the near future, as developments are following the trend of miniaturization in all fields. Literature shows that the heat exchanger research related to the performance study of heat exchangers using CFD models. This work studies the CFD simulation of heat exchanger flow and conjugates heat transfer using nano fluids through the different types of cross sections of the heat exchangers.

The present work is undertaken to study the following aspects of

1. Computational Fluid Dynamics modeling and simulation of single-phase heat exchanger to

using nano fluids understand its hydrodynamic and thermal behavior.

2. Validation of the CFD models by comparing the present simulated results with the data available in the open literature.

3. INTRODUCTION TO THE NANO FLUIDS

Nanofluids are fluids containing nanoparticles (nanometer-sized particles of metals, oxides, carbides, nitrides, or nanotubes). Nanofluids exhibit enhanced thermal properties, amongst them; higher thermal conductivity and heat transfer coefficients compared to the base fluid. Simulations of the cooling system of a large truck engine indicate that replacement of the conventional engine coolant (ethylene glycol-water mixture) by a nanofluid would provide considerable benefits by removing more heat from the engine. "Tiny" means no larger than a few nanometers — billionths of a meter. They are made by suspending materials like copper or copper oxide in liquids such as water or ethylene glycol (radiator fluid). In analysis such as computational fluid dynamics (CFD), nanofluids can be assumed to be single phase fluids and Classical theory of single phase fluids can be applied.

4.0 COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS (CFD)

CFD stands for Computational Fluid Dynamics. CFD is predicting what will happen, quantitatively, when fluids flow, often with the complications of:

- Simultaneous flow of heat,
 - Mass transfer (e.g. perspiration, dissolution),
 - Phase change (e.g. melting, freezing, boiling),
 - Chemical reaction (e.g. combustion, rusting),
- It is concerned with obtaining numerical solution to fluid flow problems.

5.0 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Heat exchangers are devices in which heat is transferred from one fluid to another. Common examples of heat exchanger are the radiators of car, condenser at the back of the domestic refrigerator etc. A transfer type of heat exchanger is one in which both fluids pass simultaneously through the device and heat is transferred through separating walls. Transfer type of exchanger are further classified as

- (a) Parallel flow type
- (b) Counter flow type
- (c) Cross flow.

A simple heat exchanger of transfer type can in the form of tube arrangement flowing through the inner tube and the other through the annulus surrounding it. Transfer takes place across the walls of the inner tube.

The apparatus consist of a concentric tube heat exchanger. The hot fluid i.e., hot water is obtained from an electric geyser and it flows through the inner tube. The cold fluid is coldwater can be admitted at any one of the ends enabling the heat transfer to run as a parallel flow apparatus. This can be done by operating the different values provided. Temperature of the fluids can be measure using thermocouples. Flow rate can be watch and measuring jar. The outer tube is provided with adequate asbestos rope insulation to minimize the surroundings.

Figure 1: Experimental Setup

Fig2; Thermocouple junction

Fig3: Thermostat

LINEDIAGRAM;

Figure4: line diagram of heat exchanger

5.1 SPECIFICATIONS:

- Length of the heat exchanger (L):1000cm.
- Inner copper tube-outer diameter (d_o): 23mm.
- Inner copper pipe inner diameter (d_i): 22mm.
- Outer pipe outer diameter: 58mm.
- Outer pipe inner diameter: 53mm.
- Hot water Motor: 4liters/min .
- Cold water motor: 2liters/min.
- Thermocouple: k type
- Heater: 230v/15 A/ 50 HZ

6.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 calculations for water-parallel flow

Sl.no	Hot water side			Cold water side		
	Flow rate cc/sec	Inlet temp T1	Outlet temp T3	Flow rate cc/sec	Inlet temp T2	Outlet temp T4
1.	830/20	80	73	280/20	31	33

6.2 calculations for water-counter flow

Sl.no	Hot water side	Cold water side

	Flow rate cc/sec	Inlet temp T1	Outlet temp T3	Flow rate cc/sec	Inlet temp T2	Outlet temp T4
1.	830/20	70	66	280/20	37	39

6.3 calculations for carbon powder:-parallel flow

Sl.no	Hot water side			Cold water side		
	Flow rate cc/sec	Inlet temp T1	Outlet temp T3	Flow rate cc/sec	Inlet temp T2	Outlet temp T4
1.	830/20	70	66	280/20	37	39

6.4 calculations for carbon powder:-counter flow

Sl.no	Hot water side			Cold water side		
	Flow rate cc/sec	Inlet temp T1	Outlet temp T3	Flow rate cc/sec	Inlet temp T2	Outlet temp T4
1.	830/20	70	66	280/20	46	47

7.0 ANSYS FLUENT

➤ *Designing*

➤ *Meshing:*

➤ Pressure

➤ pathline

➤ velocity

➤ temperature

7.1 WATER PARALLEL FLOW

7.2 WATER COUNTER FLOW

➤ Pressure

➤ pressure

➤ Temperature;

➤ temperature

➤ velocity

7.3 CARBON POWDER-PARALLEL FLOW

7.4 CARBON POWDER-COUNTER FLOW

8.0 DISCUSSION

Difference between Experimental & Theoretical By Graphs:

8.1 WATER: Parallel Hot;

8.2 water -Parallel cold;

8.3 water -Counter Hot;

8.4 water -Counter cold

9.0 CARBON POWDER:

9.1 carbon power-Parallel Hot;

9.2 carbon powder Parallel Cold;

9.3 carbon powder- Counter Hot;

9.4 carbon powder -Counter Cold;

11.0 FUTURE SCOPE OF THE WORK

By using the above concept Convective heat transfer coefficient of nano fluids in a heat exchanger with different shapes of longitudinal strip inserts analysis can also be done with commercially available computational fluid dynamics software FLUENT.

Water based nano fluids containing various volume fractions of nano particles of Titanium oxide are used to study the effect of increase in the heat transfer coefficient. Thermo physical properties nano fluids are considered for heat transfer coefficient by assuming nano fluids in a single phase for future study.

11.0 CONCLUSION

The above calculations show us that the effectiveness of the double pipe heat exchanger changes from 19% to 29% between parallel and counter flow with water. When carbon particles mix with water the effectiveness of this type of heat exchanger is increased by 10% in both parallel and counter flow. And we also have same results in fluent with a difference of negligible variance. Hence results confirm that suspension of carbon particles in water offers higher heat exchange capacity than normal water. This study analyzes the characteristics of carbon with mixture gives more heat transfer.

REFERENCE

[1]RC Sachdeva: Heat and Mass transfer.
 [2]Chai JM, Patnakar SV: Laminar Natural convection in internally finned horizontal annuli.
 [3]Ho CJ, Lin YH, Chen TC: A numerical study of natural convection in concentric cylinders with fixed boundary conditions.
 [4]Eymard, R. Gallouët, T. R. Herbin, R. (2000) The finite volume method Handbook of Numerical Analysis, Vol. VII, 2000, p. 713-1020. Editors: P.G. Ciarlet and J.L. Lions
 [5]Choi, S. U. S., Enhancing Thermal Conductivity of Fluids with Nanoparticles, in: Development and Applications of Non-Newtonian Flows (Eds. D. A. Singer, H. P. Wang), ASME, New York, USA, FED vol. 66, 1995, pp. 99-103.
 [6]Yang, Y., et al., Heat Transfer Properties of Nanoparticle in Fluid Dispersions in Laminar Flow, International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer, 48 (2005), 6, pp. 1107-1116.

[7]Wen, D., Ding, Y., Experimental Investigation into Convective Heat Transfer of Nanofluids at the Entrance Region under Laminar Flow Conditions. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 47 (2004) 24, pp. 5181-5188

[8]Pantzali, M. N., Mouza, A. A., Paras, S. V., Investigating the Efficacy of Nanofluids as Coolants in Plate Heat Exchangers (PHE), *Chemical Engineering Science*, 64 (2009), 14, pp. 3290-3300

[9]Mapa, L. B., Mazhar, S., Heat Transfer in the Mini Heat Exchanger using Nanofluids, *American Society for Engineering Education*, 2005 IL/IN Sectional Conference, 2005 – Northern Illinois University, DeKalb, Ill., USA

[10]Duangthongsuk, W., Wongwises, S., Heat Transfer Enhancement and Pressure Drop Characteristics of TiO₂-Water Nanofluid in a Double-Tube Counter Flow Heat Exchanger, *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 52 (2009), 7-8, pp. 2059-2067.

[11]Rennie, T. J., Raghavan, V. G. S., Numerical Studies of a Double-Pipe Helical Heat Exchanger, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 26 (2006), 11-12, pp. 1266-1273.

[12]Kanaris, A. G., Mouza, A. A., Paras, S. V., Flow and Heat Transfer Prediction in a Corrugated Plate Heat Exchanger using a CFD Code, *Chemical Engineering Technology*, 29 (2006), 8, pp. 923-930

[13]Pantzali, M. N., et al., Effect of Nanofluids on the Performance of a Miniature Plate Heat Exchanger with Modulated Surface, *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow*, 30 (2009), 4, pp. 691-699